

A PROPOSAL FOR A KEY-GENERATION FRAMEWORK BASED ON R-ADIC INTEGER DYNAMICS

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ABSTRACT. This document establishes priority for a mathematical framework in which finite digit strings are derived from solution sets of fixed-point equations of the form $y^{\bar{\tau}(r)} = y$ in rings of r -adic integers, where $\bar{\tau}(r)$ equals $A391966(r)$ (for integers $r = 2, 3, 4, \dots$) on the OEIS. A central feature of the construction is the separation between the choice of the r -adic modulus and the choice of the exponent governing the fixed-point equation, together with a principled restriction preventing structural degeneracies. A deterministic, purely combinatorial digit-extraction mechanism is then outlined. No cryptographic security claim is made; the sole purpose of this note is to preserve authorship of the underlying mathematical idea via public disclosure.

1. INTRODUCTION

The constructions described in this note emerged in 2020, during the author’s long-term investigation into integer tetration and, more specifically, into the phenomenon known as *constancy of the congruence speed* [4, 6] in radix- r numeral systems (see [5]), with $r > 1$ arbitrary. The study of stabilization patterns for the rightmost digits of iterated power towers naturally leads to the analysis of fixed-point equations over rings of r -adic integers $\mathbb{Z}_r := \varprojlim_n \frac{\mathbb{Z}}{r^n \mathbb{Z}}$ [3].

Let τ be an integer greater than 1. Then, for each integer $r > 1$, the number of solutions of

$$y^\tau = y$$

in \mathbb{Z}_r depends on both the arithmetic structure of r and the value of the exponent τ .

It is a classical fact that, for every r , there exists a smallest integer $\bar{\tau}(r) > 1$ such that $y^\tau = y$ admits a maximal set of r -adic solutions: a compact formula for the exact value of $\bar{\tau}(r)$ is provided by Equation (2) of [3] (for the related OEIS sequence see [2]).

Although these results were originally developed in a purely number-theoretic context, they suggest a more general structural question: “How do the solution sets of $y^\tau = y$ in \mathbb{Z}_r behave when the exponent varies *below* the stabilization threshold?”

The present work isolates this aspect and reformulates it in a way that allows the modulus and the exponent to be selected independently, subject to a constraint induced by the admissible domain of moduli.

2. CHOICE OF THE MODULUS

Fix once and for all a public domain \mathcal{D} consisting of squarefree integers $r > 29$ with at least three distinct prime divisors (for instance, one may restrict to moduli r of moderate size, e.g., on the order of a few million, to keep computations inexpensive). The set \mathcal{D} need not be contiguous and may contain gaps; its purpose is to control the arithmetic behavior of the associated fixed-point equations. No secrecy is assumed for \mathcal{D} .

Since r is assumed to be squarefree by hypothesis, $\text{rad}(r) = r$ immediately follows.

Thus, $r \in \mathcal{D}$ and we are interested in the nontrivial solutions of $y^\tau = y$ in $\mathbb{Z}_r := \varprojlim_{m \geq 1} \mathbb{Z}/r^m\mathbb{Z}$ (i.e., the ring of r -adic integers).

Associated with the domain \mathcal{D} is the integer $\bar{\tau}(r) > 1$ defined in [3], where $\bar{\tau}(r)$ denotes the smallest exponent for which $y^\tau = y$ has a maximal solution set in \mathbb{Z}_r . The exact cardinality of this maximal solution set (including the trivial solution $y = 0$) is given in [3] and recorded in the OEIS sequence [1].

3. CHOICE OF THE EXPONENT

An exponent $\tilde{\tau}$ is chosen by Bob, after a specific modulus $r \in \mathcal{D}$ has been fixed, and it is constrained only by the admissible range induced by the domain \mathcal{D} . For instance, it is reasonable to assume that

$$\tilde{\tau} \in \left[\left\lceil \frac{\bar{\tau}(r) + 1}{2} \right\rceil, \bar{\tau}(r) \right].$$

This restriction has a precise structural meaning. Let c be an arbitrary positive integer. For every integer $r > 1$, there exists an integer $m(r) > 1$ such that the solution set of $y^{\bar{\tau}(r)+c \cdot m(r)} = y$ stabilizes, and larger exponents of the form $\bar{\tau}(r) + c \cdot m(r)$ do not produce new r -adic solutions. Allowing $\tilde{\tau} > \bar{\tau}(r)$ would therefore lead to unavoidable repetitions across the domain \mathcal{D} . By contrast, the above interval ensures that $\tilde{\tau}$ is never too small (avoiding trivial regimes) and never exceeds the stabilization threshold for any admissible modulus.

No parity condition on $\tilde{\tau}$ is imposed. Possible symmetries in the solution sets are handled explicitly at a later stage.

Remark 1. *It is worth noting that, in settings where interoperability across a fixed public domain of moduli is required, one may further restrict the admissible range of $\tilde{\tau}$ by taking global bounds over the domain. This variant is not pursued here.*

4. STATIONARY r -ADIC BRANCHES

Let $r \in \mathcal{D}$ and let $\tilde{\tau}$ be chosen as above. Consider the fixed-point equation

$$(1) \quad y^{\tilde{\tau}} = y$$

in the ring of r -adic integers \mathbb{Z}_r . We denote by $A(r, \tilde{\tau})$ the set of its solutions.

From this set, the trivial solutions 0 and 1 are discarded. If the element -1_r is a solution (i.e., if the chosen $\tilde{\tau}$ is an odd number), it is discarded as well.

It may occur that the solution set of (1) is invariant, at least partially, under the additive involution $x \mapsto -x$ in \mathbb{Z}_r , so that together with a solution x its additive inverse $-x$ is also a solution. Such pairs need not appear in an explicit symmetric form and may be represented by distinct r -adic expressions. Since the two elements of a pair $\{x, -x\}$ encode the same r -adic information up to sign, retaining both is unnecessary for the subsequent extraction procedure. Accordingly, whenever such a pair occurs, a single representative may be retained, while elements fixed by the involution (if any) are treated separately.

The resulting set will be referred to as the collection of *non-trivial stationary branches* associated with the pair $(r, \tilde{\tau})$.

5. DEPTH PARAMETER AND TRUNCATION

Introduce an integer parameter B , defined as a deterministic function of r and $\tilde{\tau}$. The role of B is to combine the two independent choices and to determine the depth at which digit extraction is performed. No specific functional form is required in general. As an example, one may take

$$B = \left\lceil \sqrt[3]{r \cdot \tilde{\tau}} \right\rceil,$$

although other choices may be equally suitable depending on the domain \mathcal{D} .

For each stationary branch

$$x = \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n \cdot r^n,$$

the B least significant base- r digits (i.e., a_0, \dots, a_{B-1}) are discarded. A window of k consecutive digits immediately to the left of this truncation point is then selected. Each stationary branch thus contributes a finite digit string of length k .

6. DYNAMIC ORDERING AND DIGIT EXTRACTION

At each iteration, the digit strings obtained from all stationary branches are ordered lexicographically in radix- r . This ordering is recomputed at every step, since the digit windows shift and the strings themselves change.

From the ordered list, the lower median string is selected (i.e., the unique median when the number of strings is odd, and the first of the two central strings when it is even). From this string, the lower central digit is extracted (i.e., the unique central digit when k is odd, and the left one of the two central digits when k is even). The digit windows are then shifted by one position and the procedure is repeated.

After N iterations, this mechanism produces a string of N digits in base r . This string may finally be mapped to any desired external numeral system, such as binary or decimal.

7. CONCLUSION

This document records authorship of a mathematical framework based on:

- r -adic fixed-point equations arising from the arithmetic of tetration;
- a domain-induced restriction on the admissible exponent range preventing structural repetition;
- a deterministic but dynamically evolving digit-extraction mechanism.

No claim is made regarding cryptographic security, efficiency, or optimality. All such aspects are intentionally left open for further investigation.

REFERENCES

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